

I am pleased to share 16 years of teachings from 2009 through 2025, offered now for your reflection during the years 2026 through 2035.

This is a sample of blog posts from my blog at <https://ccomish.blogspot.com>

May these insights illuminate and inspire your journey of Ascension.

A gift to you with love.

Peace and love to all.

2026:

January: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/01/what-is-christ-consciousness.html>

February: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/02/higher-evolution.html>

March: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/03/mass-media-programming.html>

April: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/04/pictures-of-heavenly-astral-form-soul.html>

May: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/05/prayer-for-heaven.html>

June: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/06/embody-hgher-self.html>

July: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/07/3-books-by-chris-comish.html>

August: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/08/manifest-higher-self.html>

September: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/09/oversoul.html>

October: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/10/choice.html>

November: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/11/faithwill.html>

December: https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/12/frequency_31.html

2027:

January: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/01/ascension-experiences.html>

February: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/02/free-will-choice.html>

March: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/03/space-time-and-time-space-differences.html>

April: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/04/pictures-of-heavenly-astral-form-soul.html>

May: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/05/other-selves.html>

June: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/06/higher-self-balance.html>

July: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/07/message-to-disciples.html>

August: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/08/soul-trajectory.html>

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October: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/10/perfect.html>

November: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/11/god-is-within.html>

December: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/12/that-which-is-not.html>

2028:

January: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/01/balancing-love-and-wisdom.html>

February: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/02/a-holy-prayer.html>

March: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/03/we-are-all-one.html>

April: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/04/the-void-nirvana.html>

May: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/05/unity-in-diversity.html>

June: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/06/become-higher-self.html>

July: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/07/distant-healing-network.html>

August: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/08/lightbody-6th-density.html>

September: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/09/oversoul-merger.html>

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November: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/11/one.html>

December: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/12/god-is-all-that-is.html>

2029:

January: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/01/christ-bodhisattva-avatar-vow.html>

February: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/02/manifest-higher-self.html>

March: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/03/electro-magnetic-connections.html>

April: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/04/kundalini-rise.html>

May: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/05/density-level-of-council-of-twelve.html>

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July: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/07/7-refinement-of-physical-body.html>

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October: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/10/sixth-density.html>

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December: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/12/be-bridge.html>

2030:

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February: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/02/higher-evolution.html>

March: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/03/what-you-choose-for-yourself-give-to.html>

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2031:

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2033:

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2034:

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February: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2011/02/dream-and-more.html>

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2035:

January: <https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/01/balance.html>

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Extra Gifts

How are Chris Comish's attunements or healing sessions created?

<https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2023/09/how-are-chris-comishs-attunements.html>

How Attunements and Healing Sessions are received forever

<https://ccomish.blogspot.com/2025/08/how-attunements-and-healing-sessions.html>